

NOTES

Beryllium(II), Magnesium(II) and Calcium(II) Complexes of Amethopterin

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COMPLEX formation of drugs with metal ions has been suggested as one of the important mechanisms of drug action¹. Among the alkaline earth group metal ions, Be^{II} forms the largest number and the most stable complexes. Due to the higher stability of the Be^{II} complexes with biologically important oxygen donor ligands², Be^{II} ion is considerably toxic. Magnesium and calcium ions are biologically essential. Although complexes of Be^{II} and Mg^{II} with many drugs have been studied^{3,4}, no information is available on complex formation of these ions with amethopterin (1), a structural analogue of normal pteroyl compound folic acid antagonist, which has been shown quite important in experimental cancer therapy mainly in leukemia⁵.

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The present paper describes pH-metric study of the complex of amethopterin (4-amino-N¹⁰-methyl-pteroylglutamic acid) with Be^{II}, Mg^{II} and Ca^{II} using Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique⁶ as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁷ at 35° and at 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 M ionic strengths (KNO₃).

Experimental

All the chemicals employed were of AnalaR grade. The solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. Stoichiometry and the values of various formation constants were computed as described elsewhere⁸. Solution of amethopterin was prepared by percolating an aqueous solution of the sodium salt (Lederate) through the cation-exchange resin Amberlite IR-120 (H-form). The ligand regenerated acid was standardised against a standard alkali (KOH).

The following mixtures (initial volume 50 ml) were pH-metrically titrated with a 0.1 M KOH in

nitrogen atmosphere at 30°: (i) 5 ml of 0.02 M HNO₃; (ii), (i)+20 ml of 0.004 M AMPGA solution; and (iii), (ii)+5 ml of 0.002 M metal ion solution. The ionic strengths of the solution were maintained at 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 M by adding the required amount of KNO₃. The possibility of the formation of polynuclear complexes has been minimised with the use of very dilute solutions (2 × 10⁻⁴ M) of the metal ions.

The values of $\bar{n}$, $\bar{n}H$ and pL^- were calculated using the Irving-Rossotti equations⁷. The values of the formation constant (K) were computed by the method of least-square (Table 1). The thermodynamic stability constants (K°) were obtained by extrapolating the values of $\log K$ to zero ionic strengths.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF AMPGA COMPLEXES WITH Be^{II}, Mg^{II} AND Ca^{II} AT 35° AND VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTHS

Ionic strength	log K_n	Be ^{II}	Mg ^{II}	Ca ^{II}
0.2 M	log K_1	8.90	8.75	8.75
	log K_2	7.15	6.60	6.65
0.1 M	log K_1	7.80	7.70	7.65
	log K_2	6.50	5.65	6.60
0.05 M	log K_1	7.20	6.90	6.80
	log K_2	6.15	5.25	5.15
0	log K_1°	6.00	5.15	5.05
	log K_2°	5.55	4.25	4.20

Results and Discussion

Preliminary conductometric and potentiometric (pH) titrations, using monovariation method of Nair and Pande⁹, indicate formation of ML and ML₂ complexes with amethopterin, where AMPGA = LH₂ and M = Be, Mg and Ca. The maximum values of $\bar{n}$ (~2) confirm the formation of two complexes, ML and ML₂. Further, pH-titration curves (Fig. 1) reveal that in all cases, two protons are released during complexation of each molecule of the ligand. Thus the reactions may be represented as

It is interesting to note that during the titration, no precipitate was obtained with any of the metals used in the investigation.

A perusal of Table 1 indicates that the stability constants of the metal complexes increase with decreasing size of the metal ion, Be^{II} > Mg^{II} > Ca^{II}. Further, with the increasing ionic strength, the values of formation constant were found to increase

Fig. 1. pH-titrations: (A) acid, (B) ligand and (C) metal.

almost regularly. This observation is quite reverse of the same obtained by Nayan and Dey¹⁰ in case of folic acid complexes, showing quite different mechanism for the metal–ligand interaction in case of amethopterin.

The values of formation constants obtained for the metal complexes studied here are very much higher than those reported for the folic acid complexes¹⁰. The observed enhanced stability of amethopterin complexes seems quite logical in the light of higher $\log K_f^H$ value for amethopterin^{8,11}, viz. $\log K_f^H$ for folic acid, 6.55 at 30°, and for AMPGA, 7.65 at 35°; $\log K_1$ for Be^{II}–folic acid, 4.80 at 30°, and for Be^{II}–AMPGA, 7.20 at 35°, at $\mu=0.05 M$.

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Praseodymium(III), Neodymium(III), Samarium(III), Holmium(III) and Erbium(III) Complexes with 3-(3-Hydroxy-2-naphthalideneimino)propanoic Acid and *N*-Salicylideneisovaleric Acid as Ligands

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LANTHANON chelates of ligands possessing oxygen and nitrogen donor atoms find application as bactericides and fungicides. 3-(3-Hydroxy-2-naphthalideneamino)propanoic acid (H_2NP) and *N*-salicylideneisovaleric acid (H_2SI) also possess such donor sites. A perusal of the literature has indicated that no studies have been made on Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Ho^{III} and Er^{III} complexes with H_2NP and H_2SI . The present paper describes the findings on such compounds.

Experimental

The ligands H_2NP and H_2SI were prepared as reported earlier¹. The solid complexes of H_2NP and H_2SI with the lanthanons under study were prepared by the method reported earlier². The results of elemental analyses, molar conductance and molecular mass are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis and molecular mass data suggest 1 : 2 (metal–ligand) stoichiometry for all the compounds. The conductance data indicate their non-electrolytic nature (Table 1).

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of the complexes (Table 2) showed a shift in band position towards the lower wave numbers as compared to those of the aqua-complexes. The bands observed in the case of Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Ho^{III} and Er^{III} complexes could be assigned to the transitions from 3H_4 , $^4I_{9/2}$, $^6H_{5/2}$, 5I_8 and $^4I_{15/2}$ (ground levels) to the excited J levels of the respective $4f^n$ configurations. The present data also show that the nephelauxetic values for different J levels vary considerably. The $(1-\beta)$ values are used to estimate Sinha's covalency³ parameter (δ). Another bonding parameter, $b^{1/2}$, which measures the amount of $4f$ orbital–ligand-orbital mixing in these compounds were also calculated. The values of $(1-\beta)$, δ and $b^{1/2}$ at corresponding transitions are also included in Table 2. The positive values for $(1-\beta)$ and δ suggest that the bonding between metal and ligand is covalent as compared to that in the metal–aqua-ions. The average values of δ are positive, but smaller than unity in the case of complexes derived from H_2SI . It indicates weaker covalent bonding in H_2SI complexes than in those of H_2NP complexes. The $b^{1/2}$ values are higher for the H_2NP